

As on 31-03-2020, the following data entry procedures are recommended in order to add records of metadata into the knowledge base system. 'Metadata' is a set of information about the recorded data. Creating a 'Metadata' record is **compulsory for every record of crop data gathered in every table**.

1. There are 16 fields to be entered in the '**Metadata**' table, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Metadata ID (Auto-generated)

- This is the record number of the table.
- Each Metadata record has their own unique ID. This ID is linked to all recorded data in the database.

1.2 Contributor (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the name of the person who created the record.

1.3 Date (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the date when the record is created.
- Date **MUST** be recorded according to the date of data being recorded.

1.4 Ref1 (Compulsory)

- This field is referring to the link/URL of the source.
- Ensure the link provided is accessible for public user
- Refer to "*SOP - Recording Metadata 'Ref' and 'Src'*"

1.5 Src1 (compulsory)

- This is referring to the source of reference to be written in APA format (recommended format).
- Refer to "*SOP - Recording Metadata 'Ref' and 'Src'*"

1.6 Accuracy Flag

- Flag given to indicate the accuracy of the data from the source
- In database, this field presented as drop-down menu with the selection of:
 - i) Green – reliable source
 - ii) Amber – uncertain source
 - iii) Red – non-reliable source
- Refer to "*SOP - Recording Accuracy Flag*"

1.7 Location

- This field is referring to the location where the information in the source is applied to.
- Location **MUST** be entered as **GLOBAL**, if there is no specific location mentioned in the source.

Draft status

1.8 Ref2

- The link/URL of the second source

1.9 Src2

- Source of the second reference to be written in APA format (recommended format)

2.0 Accuracy Flag

- Accuracy flag of second source

2.1 Location

- Location of second source

2.2 Ref3

- The link/URL of the third source

2.3 Src3

- Source of the third reference to be written in APA format (recommended format)

2.4 Accuracy Flag

- Accuracy flag of third source

2.5 Location

- Location of third source

2.6 Image

- The image is related to the metadata record.

2.7 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the source or recorded data itself.